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The Impact of Human Resource Management on Organizational Brand By the Mediating Role of Employee Competence, Commitment, and Satisfaction in the Insurance Industry

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ABSTRACT

Today, paying attention to employees and aligning their features and capabilities with the brand is of great importance for organizations in competitive environments. According to previous studies, factors such as competency, satisfaction, and commitment have been used as mediators between HRM and the brand of the organization. The statistical population of the study consisted of 270 employees of different branches of social security insurance in Alborz province. The sample size was determined based on Morgan's table and 220 questionnaires were distributed and 159 correct questionnaires returned. The validity of the questionnaire was confirmed by an interview with industry experts and its reliability was confirmed by Cronbach's alpha coefficient at 0.854. Confirmatory factor analysis, structural equation modeling (SEM), AMOS and SPSS software were used for data analysis. The results showed that the conceptual model of the research has good fitness. After examining 9 direct hypotheses and 3 hypotheses with mediating variables, it was concluded that the main research hypothesis about the relationship between HRM and brand and 6 other hypotheses was positive and significant. Also, the relationship between HRM with competence and competence with the brand was not significant and the variable mediating role of competence between HRM and brand is not confirmed, but two variables of commitment and satisfaction can play a mediating role in the relationship between HRM and brand. Therefore, organizations can enhance the brand of the organization by measuring, planning and continuously improving HRM indicators and adopting strategies to increase employee commitment and satisfaction, and increase customer satisfaction by increasing sales and profits.

Keywords: Brand, Human Resources Branding, Commitment, Satisfaction, Competency, Mediator Variable.

Introduction

Branding is a way of achieving a specific social architecture and a combination of organizational values that drive employees steadily into a single behavior and pattern. The cultural pattern that unconsciously generates defined values and behaviors as each new employee enters and reproduces organizational values like a factory. Ultimately, an internal branding program is expected to lead to a social paradigm that is a form of sustainable competitive advantage. It is a combination of human beings, values, and behaviors that simply cannot be imitated by any other organization (Wallace, de Chernatony, & Buil, 2013).

For nearly two decades, human resource brand development (employer brand) has been one of the concepts that have been discussed in the marketing and human resources literature. Although there are various definitions of this concept, it can be seen as an image of the characteristics of an organization (in the role of the employer) in the minds of internal employees and job seekers in the labor market. An organization's positive brand reflects the traits that make the organization have characteristics in the minds of its employees and job seekers that make it an ideal working environment. The efforts of leading organizations to recruit, nurture, retain, and deploy knowledge-based forces will ensure their competitive advantage today and tomorrow (Sheida, Hemmati, & Fakhari, 2014).

Nowadays, many organizations are directing their large investments towards branding to have a strong and valuable brand, with the aim of reaching their audiences through communication and advertising and creating a more appropriate and superior to their competitors in the audience's mind, because they believe customers' minds play a key role in their decision to buy. On the other hand, each employee of the organization as a product or service element will be an effect on customers and on each other and sometimes will have far more impact than advertising on customers (Hosseini, Mousavi, & Ziaie-Bideh, 2013).

Internal branding with the goal of achieving employee-specific brand equity is a new strategy to ensure that employees comply with brand commitments. Since in service organizations, employees are able to influence customer perceptions and purchasing decisions and thus play a key role in the success of the organization, enhancing employee-specific brand equity can create a lasting competitive advantage for the organization (Sanavifard, 2014).

In this study, first, the basic concepts about the brand, human resource branding, competence, commitment and loyalty of staff are defined and in the following sections, we will refer to previous research, method and hypothesis analysis and finally to conclusions and suggestions.

1. Theoretical foundations and research background

Since the present value of the organization is due to the reinforcement of employee behavior, new values in the organization must also be targeted in behavior (Punjaisri, & Wilson, 2011). Among the factors that can influence the appropriate context for strengthening the brand of the organization, such as competence, commitment, and employee satisfaction in the organization (Stoner, 1995). In this case, human resource management can have a significant impact on the brand equity of the organization. In this research, the impact of HRM on the brand of the organization is tested through the mediation of competence, commitment, and satisfaction.

1-2. Human Resources Management at IDRO

In human resource management, recruitment systems mean exploring and selecting the right talent for global education, developing meaning in training and resolving short-term problems, planning conceptualization, concept retention, institutionalizing professional behaviors, which needs to be followed up by appropriate context and the creation of appropriate cultures, as well as the formulation of procedures or even the suggestion of laws appropriate to the subject, the evaluation is a way to refine management practices and get feedback from current operations and ultimately provide a foundation for the growth and promotion of the HRM culture in the organization (Mohammadi, & Varzeshkar, 2008).

Human resource management consists of a regular set of activities that are logically organized and convert inputs into outputs to achieve a specific purpose (Checkland, 1981). In some form of segmentation, the human resource management system in IDRO is divided into five general categories:

1-2-1-Human Resource Planning Process: Human Resource Planning means managing employees in an organization's human resources planning; policies and actions required to perform a part of the management task that depends on aspects of the employee's performance, particularly for hiring, staff training, performance evaluation, giving reward and create a healthy and fair environment for the organization's employees (Hamidi, & Sarfarazi, 2015).

1-2-2-Human Resources Training Process: Training is a key factor in development that, if properly planned and implemented, can have significant economic returns. Staff training and improvement is also a strategic measure that promotes job quality at the individual level and contributes to the development of the organization at the organizational level and increases productivity at the national level. Therefore, it is the most fundamental measure that underpins change in organizations (Sa'adat, 2014).

2-1-3-Human Resources Recruitment Process: One of the most important HRM processes is recruiting and hiring the required human resources. Today, given the immediate need for skilled human resources, we have to contact job seekers all the time and constantly review their scientific and professional information and records so each unit in the organization needs to be manned, HR managers can provide the unit with the least cost at the lowest cost possible (Sa'adat, 2014).

2-1-4-Human Resources Compensation Process: Compensation for services is any kind of consideration and value that an employer or organization pays for the work done by the organization; services that the organization compensates for include financial compensation and non-financial compensation (Agyen-Gyasi, & Boating, 2015).

2-1-5-Human Resources Performance Assessment Process: The evaluation of performance and management of the designed process to improve organizational performance is an individual program team designed by managers. Although it is a difficult process for managers and organizational staff to perform better, it ultimately leads to improved organizational performance. The performance appraisal is a process in which the performance of an individual and organization or corporate entity is evaluated. This formal process evaluates and observes the

overall performance of the organization. The performance evaluation is usually done annually (Averbook, 2005).

2-2-Organizational Brand

In general, any concept needs to be defined. Many concepts have different meanings to various professionals. Since each researcher views the concept in terms of his or her mental framework, a multitude of definitions and interpretations are natural and unavoidable. The brand is also one of the concepts that have different definitions, so it is tried to refer to the most definitive definitions in this article. The US Marketing Committee defines a brand: "Brand is a name, word, symbol, design or combination of them that aims to identify the products or services of a salesperson or a group of retailers to customers, as well as to distinguish their products from other competitors and a brand adds dimensions to a product or service to distinguish that product or service from others. These distinctions can be logical, tangible or even intangible (Johansson, 2008).

2-3-Human Resources Branding

In human resources management, brand jobs are analyzed based on business processes. Organizational positions are arranged by business process facilitators. The goals of the brand are linked to the appraisal mechanism and the salaries and remuneration of the employees. The recruitment system is organized in such a way that brand goals play a key role. Welfare programs are designed to support the essence of the brand. Before the organization's brand communication and psychological problems are created by the organization, it is identified by periodic interviews with the brand's HR consultant. According to the defined values of the organization, training is provided and employees develop their skills and knowledge while working in the organization.

2-4-Competency

Since competency management determines the key knowledge needed by the individual and the organization to achieve the goals, it can play a major role at the individual and organizational levels. The competency approach in human resource management lies at the center of key human resource concepts such as selection and evaluation of performance, management, training, development and reward management. Competency management is closely linked to the organization's efforts to create a system of employee empowerment to enhance competitive advantage, innovation and effectiveness. In addition, competency management is directly related to the organization's activities for enhancing internal knowledge and the continuous application of knowledge management. Human capital is one of the most important assets of any organization. The effective use of human capital provides the foundation for the success of the organization and the achievement of its goals. Various authors have provided different definitions of competency. Competence is cognitive (such as knowledge and skill), emotional (such as attitudes and values), behavioral and motivational attributes that enable one to perform successfully in a particular job or position. Competence represents a combination of motivation, traits, self-concept, attitudes, and values, the content of knowledge or behavioral skills that can distinguish between average and superior employees. Areas of competence represent activities that the individual is skilled at, while individual-based competencies are a set of traits that enable the individual to be competent

in a particular field. In fact, areas of competence are generally job-based, whereas competencies are essentially individual-based (Mohammadi-Zanjirani, Eshtiaghian, & Raznahan, 2012).

2-5-Staff commitment

Counter considers the commitment of individuals to give their energy of loyalty to the social system. Solansic regards commitment as a state in which the individual continues his activities and maintains his participation in them. Sheldon defines organizational commitment as a tendency, attitude, or orientation that relates one's identity to the organization and creates a similarity between the organization and the member (Whiteoak, & Mohamed, 2016).

2-6-Staff Satisfaction

Fisher and Hanna view job satisfaction as an intrinsic factor and a kind of emotional adjustment to the job and employment conditions, that is, if the job in question provides the person with the desired pleasure, he or she is satisfied with the job. Conversely, if the job does not give the person the desired pleasure, then he will not enjoy his job and seek to change it (Alipour, & Farid, 2017).

The creation of job satisfaction for employees is probably not going to be very fast, but it is definitely going to disappear very quickly. All conditions may be overwhelming to keep employee satisfaction high, but only with an inappropriate managerial approach can the effect of these appropriate conditions be tangibly zero. The definition of job satisfaction indicates that this concept reflects the positive feelings and attitudes a person has toward their job. When it is said that one has a high level of job satisfaction, that is, he/she generally likes his/her job and values it very much (Ahmad, & Daud, 2016).

2-7-Research Background

Given the new concepts of human resources branding and brand equity based on staff, quantitative research work has been done in Iran at the credible level and few empirical kinds of research have been done on Iran and other countries, which the following is a summary of their results.

Table 1. Research background in Iran

Summary of results	Research subject	Researcher (Year)
The impact of human resource management has been effective in improving the effectiveness of the organization at an alpha level of 0.01%.	The Effect of Human Resource Management on Improving the Effectiveness of Staff at Azad University East Tehran Branch	Eivazzadeh & Moeinan (2011)
Organizational commitment of employees can feel satisfaction, affiliation, and attachment to the organization, better job performance, reduce employee exit, active social behavior, absenteeism, altruism and assistance to co-workers, and reducing job stress financial success and increased effectiveness and productivity of the organization.	The effect of organizational commitment on organizational performance	Bagheri & Tavalai (2010)
The research found that the intra-organizational environment is effective in creating brand names.	Understanding the effective and determining factors within an organization to create a valuable brand name and trademark	Kaffashpour & Niakan (2011)

Employee feedback, brand intrarelationship, and brand branding have a positive and significant effect on employee-specific brand equity. Other findings of this study suggest a valid model for measuring brand equity based on employees.	Providing a Model for Explaining Employee-Based Brand Equity in Commercial Insurance in Yazd Province	Hosseini et al., (2013)
The results showed a positive relationship between research variables and fitness of the conceptual model of research.	Analyzing the Role of Human Resources on Brand Success and Presenting a Conceptual model	Sheida et al., (2014)
Organizational commitment, employee rewards, teamwork in the organization, organizational structure, and organizational communication have a significant relationship with the fulfillment of brand promises and these variables can have a direct impact on the organization.	Investigating the Impact of Organizational Climate Dimensions on Brand Promise Fulfillment	Ghorbanifard, Hashemnia, Mousavi, (2014)

Table 2. Research background in other countries

Summary of results	Research Subject	Researcher (Year)
Intrinsic Brand Equity= Brand Loyalty + Brand Intrinsic Behavior + Brand Extraversion Brand commitment→ Employee-specific value Brand knowledge→ Employee-specific value	An empirically-tested model of internal brand equity in a business-to-business setting	Baumgarth, & Schmidt, (2010)
Employee commitment to the brand→ customer-specific value	Service brand equity and employee brand commitment	Kimpakorn, & Tocquer, (2010)
The level of internal branding has a relatively high, yet very positive, impact on the level of quality commitment.	impact of internal branding on service employee's quality commitment-study on i.t solution sector of Pakistan	Gull, & Ashraf, (2012)
Brand commitment→ to Brand Citizenship Behavior Brand Citizenship Behavior→ Quality of customer relationship with the brand Internal brand communication→ Brand commitment Brand-based human resource management→ Brand commitment	.Building brand commitment: a behavioral approach to internal brand management	Burmann, & Zeplin (2012)
Employee Brand Equity Value = Brand Citizenship Behaviors + Employee Satisfaction + Brand Loyalty + Positive Verbal Advertising	Employee based brand equity: A third perspective	King, & Grace, (2009)

Research hypotheses and conceptual model of research

The conceptual framework presented the five variables such as HRM (based on the IDRO HRM model), organizational competence, satisfaction, and commitment and brand, which variable of competence, commitment and satisfaction play the role of mediator variable between HRM variable and brand variable. The research variables were derived from the previous study and based on this, the research hypotheses are formulated.

The Impact of Human Resource Management on Organizational Brand

In addition to focusing on human resources branding, it also plays an effective role in the organization's recruitment and selection system. As part of the organizational volunteer recruitment filter is designed based on the layers of brand identity and personality, the expected behaviors and capabilities are planned, selecting employees in line with brand identity and personality. On the one hand, the management of reward systems, rights, and benefits, performance appraisal with respect to the motivational system and optimal brand value in human resource branding are being reconsidered. It is possible to build HR architecture in a way that different departments or groups of organizations find a different HRM program, and the motivational mechanisms of the organization are intelligently and purposefully adjusted with emphasis on strategic values and the amount of staff contact with customers. Therefore, the introduction of brand values into each part of the organization is planned using appropriate tools and its implementation can be attributed to its purposeful planning. This both enhances efficiency in training costs and enhances brand effectiveness through a strategic approach (Irannezhad, Arsi, Mousavi, 2014). Therefore, H1 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H1: *Human Resource Management has a positive and significant impact on the organization's brand.*

The Impact of Human Resource Management on Employee Competency

In the third millennium, organizations' competitive advantage includes intelligence, knowledge, wisdom, and competence of the human resource. In today's knowledge economy, intellectual property, especially human capital, is one of the most important assets of an organization and the success of organizations is rooted in their intellectual abilities. Any interested community can play an effective part in the Third Millennium and face global challenges and pave the way for those interested in expanding their knowledge and developing their intellectual capacity, and basically put respect and interest in human excellence in his grand planning. On the other hand, many management experts believe that future competitive advantages will be reflected in the ability of organizations to manage knowledge and information. In achieving this goal, competency management is one of the most important issues in the field of knowledge management and this area of knowledge management is also a subject of human resource management (Khoshbakhti, Keshtidar, Zendehebudi, 2012). Therefore, H2 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H2: *HRM has a positive and significant impact on competence.*

The Impact of Human Resource Management on Employee Commitment

Studies show that there is a significant and inverse relationship between organizational non-commitment and organizational problems such as quitting, absenteeism, delay, non-participation, active involvement of labor force, low level of performance and human resource efficiency. Organizational commitment is very important because of its impact on the identity of the organization, the level of effort and quitting. The consequences of having a low-commitment staff may have bad consequences for the organization and therefore need to be addressed by management (Spencer, & Byrne, 2016). Therefore, H3 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H3: *HRM has a positive and significant impact on commitment.*

The Impact of Human Resource Management on Employee Satisfaction

Just as there is no uniform definition of the factors that create job satisfaction, different opinions have been expressed about job satisfaction theories. Prior to World War I, early studies of work-related attitudes began and continued actively in England, Europe, and the United States. Since the beginning of human social life, the phenomenon of employment has been in focus. In recent centuries, sociologists and psychologists have offered different views on work and occupation. Various aspects of work, such as inequality at work, job satisfaction, job motivation, and enhancing the productivity of work organizations have attracted the attention of scientists, scholars of management, sociology, economics and psychology (Babaeian, & Yousefi, 2014). Therefore, the H4 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H4: *HRM has a positive and significant impact on satisfaction.*

The impact of competence on employee commitment

Some organizations have not been successful in finding, growing, and retaining employees, especially those who are flexible and highly adaptable. This indicates that these organizations have difficulty identifying and utilizing the competencies of their employees to achieve their organizational goals. From a strategic management point of view, it is imperative that we continue to improve and sustain performance, which is only possible with the commitment of our employees. Therefore, there is a great deal of ambiguity about the relationship between competency management and organizational commitment that needs further investigation. Therefore, the H5 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H5: *Employee competence has a positive and significant impact on employee commitment.*

The Impact of Satisfaction on Employee Commitment

Today, the advantage of organizations overtaking each other lies not in the application of new technology, but in enhancing the confidence and commitment of employees to organizational goals. The amount of commitment to organization and job satisfaction are some of the hidden but influential factors in employees' job behavior. It is important to pay attention to the commitment of human resources, both in the public and private sectors. Recognizing and maintaining human resources is not just about keeping people in the organization, it is about creating an individual-organization interaction. Obviously, employee organization commitment will be valuable when it has a positive impact on the performance and efficiency of the organization and enhances the productivity and efficiency of the organization. One of the factors affecting employees' job satisfaction is their commitment. Research shows that organizational commitment affects employee performance and organizational outputs such as tendency to quit, sell, profitability of the firm, and employee absenteeism, so that job satisfaction and employee commitment increase the profitability of the organization and decrease service abandonment and by affecting employee performance, it leads to increased productivity, improved quality of service delivery. Job satisfaction is also one of the most important factors in a person's job success and it enhances

efficiency and also satisfaction in the individual (Mohammadi-Zanjirani et al., 2012). Therefore, the H6 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H6: Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment.

The Impact of Employee Competency on the Brand of the Organization

Competence is cognitive (such as knowledge and skill), emotional (such as attitudes and values), behavioral and motivational attributes that enable one to perform successfully in a particular job or position. Competence represents a combination of motivation, traits, self-concept, attitudes, and values, the content of knowledge or behavioral skills that can distinguish between average and superior employees. Areas of competence represent activities that the individual deserves, while individual-based competencies are the set of traits that give the individual the ability to be competent in a particular context. In fact, areas of competence are generally job-based, while competencies are essentially individual-based (Nasehifar, Sa'adat, Masoumzadehzavareh, 2010). A competence-based management system is a coherent, coordinated and systematic approach to human resource management based on a common set of competencies related to the organization's strategies and goals. The set of competencies in this system can be analyzed at three levels. Key competencies, functional competencies, and assignment competencies, each of which plays a significant role in the organizations brand (Mowen, & Minor, 2009). Therefore, H7 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H7: Employee competence has a positive and significant impact on the brand of the organization.

The impact of employee commitment on brand organization

Among the factors that reflect brand power in the market is the amount of commitment to the brand. Brand commitment can be defined as the extent to which the customer has a positive attitude toward the brand, the extent of his or her commitment to the brand, and the intention to continue communicating with the brand in the future. Commitment to the brand directly from the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the brand over time that is affected by the quality of service provided (AlModaressi, & Ziyaiibideh, 2015). Therefore, the H8 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H8: Employee commitment has a positive and significant impact on the brand of the organization.

The impact of employee satisfaction on the brand organization

Job satisfaction is a set of emotions and beliefs people have about their current jobs. Job satisfaction is one of the most important factors in job success and it contributes to increased efficiency as well as personal satisfaction. Job satisfaction means loving the conditions and requirements of a job, the conditions in which the job is done, and the reward for which it is received (Shafizadeh, & Kamrava, 2014). In today's competitive marketplace, employee satisfaction with their job and its impact on an organization's brand is a strategic requirement for sustained competitive advantage. Therefore, identifying the factors that explain the employees' satisfaction with their job position and its impact on the brand of the organization has been

considered by HR managers (Azizi, Jamali, Sannaie, 2012). Therefore, the H9 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H9: Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on the brand of the organization.

The mediating effect of variables

By combining the H2 and H7 hypotheses, it can be argued that competence can play a mediating role between the HRM variable and the organization's brand. Therefore, the HRM is capable of influencing the brand with the intermediary variable of competence. For this reason, the H10 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H10: Human resource management has a positive and significant impact on an organization's brand with the mediation of competence.

By combining the H3 and H8 hypotheses, it can be argued that commitment can mediate between HR and brand variables. Therefore, the HRM is capable of influencing the brand with the intermediary variable of commitment. For this reason, the H11 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H11: Human resource management has a positive and significant impact on an organization's brand with the mediation of commitment.

By combining the H4 and H9 hypotheses, we can say that employee satisfaction can mediate the role of HR and brand variables. Therefore, the HRM is capable of influencing the brand with the intermediary variable of employee satisfaction. For this reason, the H12 hypothesis is presented as follows:

H12: Human resource management has a positive and significant impact on organizational brand with the mediation of satisfaction.

Conceptual Model of Research:

Employees of the organization, when satisfied with their work environment, thus reinforce their competence and commitment to the workplace and brand of the organization. Therefore, they have come to believe that they are an important member of the organizational environment and can enhance their organization's brand. So overall, competence, commitment, and satisfaction can be potentially reinforced and can be reduced or enhanced under workplace experience. Based on the need to understand the impact and implementation of the human resource management system felt in the organizational context, the present study designed a model of the impact of human resource management on the organizational brand by considering competence, commitment, and satisfaction as mediating variables, as can be seen in Figure 2. To present the conceptual model of the present research, this model was designed according to the conceptual models of Gull, & Ashraf (2012) and Azizi et al. (2012).

Figure 1. Conceptual model of research (Source: Gull, & Ashraf, 2012; Azizi et al. 2012)

Research methodology

The purpose of this study is practical and descriptive in terms of data collection. Research is practical because its results can be useful in service organizations and in adopting strategies to improve it. The statistical population of this research is 270 employees of different branches of social security in Alborz province. The sample size was determined based on Morgan's table and 220 questionnaires were distributed and 159 correct questionnaires returned. Data were collected through a five-option Likert scale and a close questionnaire by direct referral to employees in a self-report manner. Factor validity was used to assess the validity of the questions. Factor validity is a form of construct validity obtained through confirmatory factor analysis. To ensure content validity, the research questionnaire was modified with the opinion of relevant professors and a number of insurance experts. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the current variables in Table 3 indicates that the reliability is confirmed.

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of current research variables

Questionnaire	Alpha	Alpha	
Human resources management	0.896	Staff commitment	0.798
Staff competence	0.864	Brand	0.899
Staff Satisfaction	0.815		

52% of the sample is staff aged between 31 and 40, making up the largest percentage of the sample. The lowest share belongs to the age group of 18-30 years with a share of 12%.69% of the respondents are male and 31% are female. The highest abundance of undergraduate education is

63% and the lowest is related to the doctoral degree with 10%. In terms of work experience, the highest frequency was in the age group of 31 to 40 years with 56% and the lowest in the age group of 18 to 30 years with 14%.

In addition, in this study, two critical indices of critical value and P-value were used to test the significance of the hypotheses. The critical value is the value obtained by dividing the “regression weight estimate” by the “standard error”. At the significance level of 0.05, the critical value should be greater than 1.96. Less than this value, the relevant parameter in the model is not considered significant, and also values less than 0.05 indicate a significant difference for the P-value calculated for the regression weights with zero at the confidence level of 0.99.

The Sobel test is also used to investigate the role of mediator variables and to determine the severity of the indirect effect of mediator variables a statistic named VAF is used. The Sobel test is also called the multivariate approach, the Delta method or the normal theory approach. This test is based on the inference theory used for direct effect to deduce the indirect effect coefficient ab . The indirect effect of ab is a sample-specific estimate of the indirect effect in the community that is subject to sampling variance. A P-value for ab can be obtained by estimating the standard error of ab and assuming that the sampling distribution of ab is normal.

In addition to the Sobel test, the VAF statistic is used to determine the severity of the indirect effect of the mediator variable, which gives a value between 0 and 1, and if this value is closer to 1, it indicates a stronger mediator effect (Davari, & Rezazadeh, 2014). In fact, this value measures the ratio of indirect effect to total effect calculated by the VAF formula (Gholizadeh, Zomorodi, Akbari, 2016).

$$VAF = \frac{a * b}{(a * b) + c}$$

The normality of data can be verified using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. This test examines the normality of the data according to the following assumptions.

H0: *Data have a normal distribution.*

H1: *Data have not a normal distribution.*

According to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the distribution of data is normal if the significance level (sig) for all variables is greater than the test level (0.05).

Table 5. The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Variable	Human resources	Competency	Commitment	Satisfaction	Brand	
<i>Number of samples</i>	159	159	159	159	159	
<i>Sample parameter</i>	Average	3.732	3.400	3.792	3.522	3.325
	St. Deviation	0.276	0.304	0.290	0.230	0.335
<i>The largest amount of difference</i>	Full	0.143	0.149	0.112	0.124	0.141
	Positive	0.061	0.149	0.112	0.124	0.111
	Negative	-0.143	-0.109	-0.104	-0.112	-0.103
Kolmogorov Smirnov index	0.717	0.744	0.559	0.619	0.326	
Meaningful	0.683	0.437	0.313	0.538	0.214	

According to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the significance level of the research variables was greater than 0.05 which confirms the H0 and rejects the research hypothesis. Therefore, it can be said that the research variables have a normal distribution and that structural equations and parametric tests can be used.

The present study used two steps to analyze the data, Step 1: Perform Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and step 2: The path coefficient used to analyze the relationships between variables and the role of mediators. Therefore, in this research, for data analysis and model validation, structural equation modeling and confirmatory factor analysis have been performed and the results of path coefficients of the relationships between variables have been investigated. AMOS software has also been used to test the hypotheses and test the model.

Data Analysis and Results

The purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between research variables and establish causal models, model testing, and modeling. Thus, the research had two fundamental issues. The first was the measurement of the relevant variables that need to be determined what the research instrument has measured and with what degree of accuracy. Second, the complex and latent causal relationships between variables that are not directly observable and through observable variables, which are undoubtedly error-prone, should be deduced and the magnitude and strength of the hidden relationships between them should be evaluated. Therefore, investigating the correlation and regression analysis with structural equation was the most appropriate method for testing the model and research hypotheses. In order to achieve the purpose of the research, firstly it was necessary to determine the relationship between observed variables and latent variables and then the correlation of the causal relationships between latent variables and causal effects and the amount of explained and unexplained variance. The theoretical model and research hypotheses were investigated by structural equation modeling. In this study, three steps were taken: (1) evaluation of the whole model fit; (2) evaluation of the measurement section of the model; and (3) evaluation of the structural section of the model. The purpose of evaluating the fit of the whole model was to determine to what extent the whole model was in agreement with the experimental data used. In evaluating the measurement part of the model, the relationships between latent variables and explicit variables with markers were investigated. The conceptual model of the research was investigated using the maximum likelihood method and the model parameters were estimated from the observed data. The results showed that the general model is significant. To judge the general model, decisions are made on the basis of the indices, the most important of which are root mean square and error indices, non-standard fit, and comparative fit. The results of the fit of the whole model showed that the theoretical model was consistent with the experimental data used. The results also showed that the observed markers were significantly related to latent variables.

Evaluating Research Conceptual Model

In this paper, the measurement method was structural equation modeling, which involved examining the relationships between all variables. One of the best indicators of the fit of structural equation models is the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). For models with a good fit, it should be less than 0.08. Therefore, models with an RMSEA of more than 0.08 have a poor fit. Another indicator of suitability is the result of dividing the value of chi-square by the degree of freedom, which should be less than 3 (Hooman, 2009).

The final model after examination and analysis is shown below.

Based on the final model, and with respect to the AMOS output, the mean squared error value was 0.06, which was less than 0.08. The chi-square was calculated as 2068.09 and the degree of freedom 983. Therefore, the value of the chi-square divided by the degree of freedom for the above model is 2.10 and less than 3, both of which are acceptable. Therefore, it is clearly seen that the relationship between all the components mentioned in the basic model of research is positive and significant. In fact, the research model is confirmed. Therefore, after validating the model, the results of the path analysis can be used to test the hypotheses and interpret them.

The following table presents the values accepted and the values obtained for the fit model for the research model through AMOS software.

Table 6. Indices for model fit

Index	Optimal value	Index value	Index	Optimal value	Index value
RMSEA	<0.08	0.06	NFI	>0.90	0.89
(X ² / df)	<3.00	2.10	NNFI	>0.95	0.92
GFI	>0.90	0.91	CFI	>0.95	0.91
AGFI	>0.9	0.9	IFI	>0.90	0.90

Table (7) shows the results of testing the hypotheses in terms of path coefficients, critical value, and significance level (P) with respect to the research hypotheses. In this table, the path coefficient values and their significance for each of the hypotheses were examined. The significance of the path coefficients was checked by P-values (probability values). If the target value is less than 0.05 and the path coefficient is significant, the hypothesis is confirmed, otherwise, the hypothesis is rejected. The nine main hypotheses along with the corresponding standard regression coefficients and the values of the partial indices are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. The nine hypotheses with the corresponding standard regression coefficient

Hypothesis	Route	Path coefficient	Critical value	P	Result
Hypothesis 1	Human Resource Management, Brand	0.2615	4.063	***	Confirmed
Hypothesis 2	Human Resource Management, Competency	0.0456	0.2580	0.369	Rejected
Hypothesis 3	Human Resource Management, Commitment	0.3654	7.6918	***	Confirmed
Hypothesis 4	Human Resource Management, Satisfaction	0.4971	4.7569	***	Confirmed
Hypothesis 5	Competency, Commitment	0.5786	4.7365	***	Confirmed
Hypothesis 6	Satisfaction, commitment	0.0852	3.5809	***	Confirmed
Hypothesis 7	Competency, Brand	0.0321	1.7325	0.236	Rejected
Hypothesis 8	Commitment, Brand	0.8986	5.3536	***	Confirmed
Hypothesis 9	Satisfaction, Brand	0.7368	7.6327	***	Confirmed

Considering Table 7 it can be concluded that:

Hypothesis 1: HRM has a positive and significant impact on the brand.

The results showed that the hypothesis is confirmed because the critical value in this hypothesis is 4.0637, which is higher than the absolute value of 1.96. Therefore, with a probability of 0.95%, it can be said that the above hypothesis is confirmed. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.2614, which indicates the impact of HRM on the brand of the organization.

Hypothesis 2: HRM has a positive and significant effect on competence.

The results of the modeling of structural equations illustrate the rejection of the hypothesis because the critical value in this hypothesis is 0.2580, which is less than the absolute value of 1.96 and the value of P for this hypothesis is greater than 0.05, which is further evidence of the rejection of this hypothesis.

Hypothesis 3: HRM has a positive and significant effect on commitment.

The results show that the hypothesis is confirmed because the critical value of this hypothesis is 7.6918 which is 1.96 higher than the absolute value so that the above hypothesis can be confirmed with a 0.95% probability. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.6354, which indicates the impact of competency on commitment.

Hypothesis 4: HRM has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction.

The results confirm the hypothesis because the critical value in this hypothesis is 4.7569, which is higher than the absolute value of 1.96. Therefore, with a probability of 0.95%, it can be said that

the above hypothesis is confirmed. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.4971, which indicates the effect of satisfaction on the brand.

Hypothesis 5: Employee competence has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment.

The results showed that the hypothesis is confirmed because the critical value in this hypothesis is 4.7365, which is higher than the absolute value of 1.96. Therefore, with a probability of 0.95%, it can be said that the above hypothesis is confirmed. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.5786, which indicates the effect of satisfaction on commitment.

Hypothesis 6: Employee satisfaction has a significant and positive effect on employee commitment.

The results showed that the hypothesis is confirmed because the critical value in this hypothesis is 3.5809, which is higher than the absolute value of 1.96. Therefore, with a probability of 0.95%, it can be said that the above hypothesis is confirmed. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.0852, which indicates the effect of satisfaction on commitment.

Hypothesis 7: Employee competence has a significant and positive impact on the brand of the organization.

The results of the modeling of structural equations illustrate the rejection of the hypothesis because the critical value in this hypothesis is 1.7325, which is less than the absolute value of 1.96 and the value of P for this hypothesis is greater than 0.05, which is further evidence of the rejection of this hypothesis.

Hypothesis 8: Employee commitment has a positive and significant impact on the brand of the organization.

The results show that the hypothesis is confirmed because the critical value in this hypothesis is 5.3536, which is higher than the absolute value of 1.96. Therefore, with a probability of 0.95%, it can be said that the above hypothesis is confirmed. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.8986, which indicates the effect of commitment on the brand.

Hypothesis 9: Employee satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on the brand of the organization.

The results show that the hypothesis is confirmed because the critical value of this hypothesis is 7.6327, which is higher than the absolute value of 1.96. Therefore, with a probability of 0.95%, it can be said that the above hypothesis is confirmed. In addition, the path coefficient in this hypothesis is 0.7368, which indicates the effect of satisfaction on brand reputation.

Table (8) shows the results of testing the hypotheses in terms of direct effect, indirect effect, total effect, T-value, and VAF along with related to the research hypotheses. According to the results, if the desired T-value obtained from the Sobel test for any of the mediator variables is greater than 1.96, it can be said that the hypothesis is confirmed at the confidence level of 0.95%;

otherwise, the hypothesis would be rejected. The VAF statistic was also used to determine the degree of the indirect effect of the mediator variable, which holds a value between 0 and 1. The closer this value is to 1, the stronger the effect of the mediator variable. In fact, this value measures the ratio of indirect effect to the total effect. The following are three hypotheses with the mediator variables.

Table 8. Results of the hypothesis of research mediator variables

Hypothesis	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Mediator variable	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Total effect	T-value	VAF	Result
10	HRM	Brand	Competency	0.261	0.007	0.268	0.071	0.02	Rejected
11	HRM	Brand	Commitment	0.261	0.320	0.581	3.312	0.55	Confirmed
12	HRM	Brand	Satisfaction	0.261	0.357	0.618	5.739	0.57	Confirmed

Considering Table 8, it can be concluded that:

Hypothesis 10: Mediated by competency, HRM has a positive and significant impact on the organizational brand.

The results of testing the Hypothesis 10 in the table above show that since the T-value obtained from the Sobel test is 0.0714, which is less than 1.96, it can be said that at the 0.95% confidence level, the effect of the competence mediator variable on the relationship between HR processes and brand reputation is not significant. Thus, Hypothesis 10 of the research is rejected. The findings indicate that employee competence cannot be a mediator variable between HRM and brand of the organization and indirectly decreases the reputation of the organization, because the VAF value showed that 0.02% of the intensity of HRM effect on organization brand can be explained indirectly by the mediator variable of competency.

Hypothesis 11: Mediated by commitment, HRM has a positive and significant impact on the organizational brand.

The results of testing the Hypothesis 11 in the table above show that since the T-value obtained from the Sobel test is 3.312, which is higher than 1.96, it can be said that at the 0.95% confidence level, the effect of the commitment mediator variable on the relationship between HR processes and brand reputation is significant. Thus, Hypothesis 11 of the research is confirmed. The findings indicate that employee commitment can be a mediator variable between HRM and brand of the organization and indirectly increases the reputation of the organization because the VAF value showed that 0.55% of the intensity of HRM effect on organization brand can be explained indirectly by the mediator variable of competency.

Hypothesis 12: Mediated by satisfaction, HRM has a positive and significant impact on the organizational brand.

The results of testing the Hypothesis 12 in the table above show that since the T-value obtained from the Sobel test is 5.739, which is higher than 1.96, it can be said that at the 0.95% confidence level, the effect of the satisfaction mediator variable on the relationship between HR processes and brand reputation is significant. Thus, Hypothesis 12 of the research is confirmed. The findings

indicate that employee satisfaction can be a mediator variable between HRM and brand of the organization and indirectly increases the reputation of the organization because the VAF value showed that 0.57% of the intensity of HRM effect on organization brand can be explained indirectly by the mediator variable of competency.

Discussion

This study used structural equation modeling to investigate the mediating role of competency, commitment, and satisfaction between human resource management (HMR) and the organization brand. After examining the research-proposed model and hypotheses, a general conclusion of the model can be obtained.

The main research hypothesis about the direct impact of HRM on the organization brand showed that the implementation of HRM to achieve brand reputation is a way to improve brand value, and can be used as a good way to promote employee competence, commitment, and satisfaction. These capabilities can serve as a foundation for enhancing brand reputation and organizational performance. The study main hypothesis was confirmed and a significant relationship between HRM and brand emerged. Given the results, the selected indicators were suitable for measuring human resource management (planning, training, recruitment, and performance appraisal and service compensation) in different branches of Social Security Insurance across Alborz province. It also provided useful feedback on the brand measurement of the insurance industry, utilizing different dimensions of service provision to increase brand reputation.

The second research hypothesis - the impact of HRM on competency - was rejected. This finding was also confirmed in previous research by Pasbani, Azarkasb, Fatehi-Khoshkanab (2012) which found a significant difference between private and public organizations in terms of competency-based management and reported that meritocracy, awareness of goals, organizational mission, and commitment to the organization were higher in private organizations. believe that competency management has been emerged in the private sector and is less visible in the public sector (Hajikarimi, Rezaeian, Hadizadeh, & BonyadiNaeini, 2012). Rahnavard, Agha, & Gheisari (2013) also state that most public agencies have unsatisfying performance due to not observing principles of meritocracy in selecting and appointing managers and staff

Correlation test between the studied variables in the third hypothesis discovered a significant relationship between HRM tasks and organizational commitment of employees. In other words, by enhancing HRM tasks, organizational commitment can be enhanced. The results of this hypothesis are in line with that of Yasini, Saadattalab, & Shirali, (2016) and Al Adresi, & Darun, (2017).

The fourth hypothesis investigated the impact of human resource management measures on job satisfaction in branches of Social Security Insurance across Alborz province. The results supported the positive effect of these measures by modeling structural equations. Although the positive effect of applying HRM measures on staff's job satisfaction has been observed in previous research (Carnevale, 2003; Becker, & Gerhart, 1996) we should pay more attention to the important effect of this variable. The results of this hypothesis are in line with the research of

Becker and Gerhart (1996), because he also found a correlation between the two variables. Additionally, we need to take a systematic look at human resource management practices and how they are applied since on the one hand, these tools transform the organization and on the other hand, they are the core of competitive advantage (Cappelli, & Crocker-Hefter, 1996; Chien, 2004) did not come to this conclusion. According to his research, human resources in public and even semi-public organizations should prioritize the organization and its goals over individual satisfaction, while the present research considers job satisfaction to be important and emphasize that even its slight impact should not be ignored. As noted, many studies acknowledge this effect, and even some consider the existence of leadership in the organization as a serious element effectiveness of using these tools (Delaney, & Huselid, 1996). For the effective use of these tools, the implementation of a knowledge-based system should be cited. In implementing this system differences in attitudes and demographic characteristics of employees should be attended, because staff sometimes negatively respond to changes in the HR department and may make changes applied by managers' ineffective (Kalleberg, & Moody, 1994).

The fifth hypothesis showed a significant relationship between employee competency and organizational commitment. Cochran (2009) and Edwards (2009) had reported the same result.

Given the sixth hypothesis - the positive effect of job satisfaction on employees' commitment in Social Security Insurance branches - job satisfaction and organizational commitment as job attitudes are significantly related. This effect was not unexpected as it was formerly confirmed by Westover, Westover, & Westover (2010) and (Gunlu, & Aksarayli, 2009), which can occur for a variety of reasons such as personality traits.

Babaei, Payidai, & Bahirayi, (2015) also reported the same. They found that the Pearson's correlation coefficient between organizational commitment and job satisfaction was 0.377, (indicating a positive correlation) meaning that with an increment in job satisfaction score, organizational commitment increases as well. In other words, enhancing job satisfaction can enhance organizational commitment. Due to the significant relationship between organizational commitment and internal/external satisfaction, job satisfaction was reviled as a predictor of organizational commitment. This study manifested a positive effect between organizational commitment and job satisfaction and showed that the higher the job satisfaction, the stronger the employees' organizational commitment will become. Organizational senior executives need to consider these two variables as well.

The seventh hypothesis - the impact of competency on the organization brand- was rejected. Results of the study of (Atafar, & Azarbayjani, 2001) confirmed that selection based on specific criteria other than meritocracy causes underemployment, absenteeism, job dissatisfaction, loss of creativity and talents, and reduced efficiency. And the effectiveness of organizations and the overall waste of resources of the organization and the reputation of the organization are reduced.

The eighth hypothesis was confirmed and a significant relationship was emerged between employee commitment and brand. (Gull, & Mubeen Ashraf, 2012) conducted a study on the impact of internal branding on the quality of service staff's commitment in IT sector in Pakistan.

He reported that internal branding had a relatively high and strong positive impact on the level of quality commitment. Four basic HR branding approaches including training, orientation, briefing, and group meeting were essentially designed to show significant and moderate levels of correlations between quality commitment and components. Influence of employee selection, age and experience on internal branding and quality commitment were also carefully examined; however, neither internal branding nor quality commitment was affected by these demographic factors (Dwivedi, & Johenson, 2013). In a research, trust and commitment were examined as mediators of consumer relation with business services. It was revealed that trust and commitment as two mediators affect consumer business services, and improve brand and consumer expectations. Trust-commitment is an axis for the customer that confirms product quality in relation to brands. Kimpakorn & Tocquer (2010) believe that one of the key resources for creating value for a service brand is the customer service experience in which employees play a key role. According to these scholars, employees' commitment to the organization brand has a positive relationship with customer-specific brand equity.

Given the ninth hypothesis, advertising and interactions of employees with different stakeholders can transmit the emotional value of a brand. Employees provide a source of information to the customer, at it is necessary to ensure that this information is consistent with senior management's willingness to understand the organization. This fact puts employees at the center of the brand-building process and demonstrates that their behavior can both enhance the brand promoted values, and undermine its credibility if it is inconsistent with those values. Therefore, the most important point is to examine the organization to determine how the values and behavior of employees can be adjusted to the brand's intended values. In 2005, Miles and Magnold found lower exhaustion and higher loyalty in both employees and customers. They observed that internal branding efforts increase employee satisfaction and decrease returns. (King & Grace , 2009) consider these findings as an indicator of job satisfaction and intention to stay. In this study, the theory is that brand citizenship behavior is an embodiment of brand internal management and yields the same positive results in job satisfaction, brand commitment, and desire to stay. The result of this hypothesis is also in line with research of (Rahimnia, Fatemi, Harandi, 2013; Du Preez, & Bendixen, 2015).

The tenth hypothesis- impact of HRM on the organization brand mediated by competency - was not admitted. In other words, employee competency cannot play a mediating role between HRM and the organization brand, and also indirectly decreases the organization's reputation. Since VAF value showed that 0.02 of HRM effect intensity on the organization brand can be explained indirectly by the competency mediator variable.

The mediating effect of employees' commitment in the relationship between HRM and brand organization was found to be significant. It indicated that employees' commitment can be a mediating variable between HRM and the organization brand, and indirectly enhances the organization brand. Since VAF value showed that 0.55 of HRM effect intensity on the organization brand can be explained indirectly by the competency mediator variable.

Given the twelfth hypothesis, the mediating effect of employees' satisfaction on the relationship between HRM and the organization brand was significant. This shows that

employees' satisfaction can be a mediating variable between HRM and the organization brand, and indirectly enhances the brand reputation. Since the VAF value showed that 0.57 of HRM effect intensity on the organization brand can be explained indirectly by the competency mediator variable.

Conclusion

Human resource branding is a relatively new approach in recruiting and retaining talented employees as well as enhancing organizations competitive ability. Involving this approach in all activities related to employee recruitment and retention (including employees screening, training, performance appraisal, career management, and motivation improvement) makes its impact stronger.

In short, human resource branding is a form of culturalization and cultural change management. According to executive experiences, attending to factors such as commitment, competency, and employees' satisfaction is necessary to bring about these changes. Shaping new behaviors and converting previous behaviors into new ones requires a reinforcement-punishment system in the organization. This system should monitor and analyze all behaviors and events of the organization, and encourage the correct ones to them reinforce their occurrence. Since the present value has been unwittingly institutionalized by past behaviors, new values must intentionally turn into behaviors. That is why human resources management is deemed an outstanding organizational asset. Incorporating human beings in the form of formal structures along with informal interactions leads to the formation of social architecture that is non-imitative and unique to any organization. The entry of the organization brand into the concept of HRM, and the impact of factors like competency commitment and satisfaction with a mediating role, reinforces the defined brand identity within an organization and creates a unique and competitive advantage.

Suggestions

Given disapproval of the competency impact in the second, seventh, and tenth hypotheses, as well as findings of previous research on the important role of competency in most private organizations, it is suggested that public organizations, including the Social Security Insurance, more carefully attend the role of competency. As mentioned before, organizations will be successful if they attract and nurture the most competent human resources. Therefore, the periodical assessment of competencies and capabilities of employees and managers based on appropriate models will help the organization to succeed and improve its performance, effectiveness, and efficiency. Due to fast changes of roles in organizations, these models should be able to predict now-and-future organizational needs. Neglecting this and not using the existing potentials will have a negative impact on the performance of different individuals and branches of Social Security Insurance across Alborz province. Benefiting appropriate approaches and experiences in Social Security Insurance will facilitate superior performance.

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